

COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION IN MANAGING KUCUR AREN TOURISM IN WONOKERTO VILLAGE, WONOSALAM JOMBANG DISTRICT

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Abstract

Law No. 10 of 2009 on tourism, which means tourism is a variety of tourist activities and supported by various facilities and services provided by the community, entrepreneurs, central government and local government. Good tourism is environmentally based and sustainable tourism to maintain the balance of nature. Tourism in Indonesia has become a sector that can be prioritized in facilities and development. In accordance with the policy direction of the National Development Planning Agency, the development of tourism institutions consists of: 1) coordinating with universities that provide undergraduate education in the field of tourism; 2) Increase the capacity and quality of tourism education institutions, expand departments and demand, build tourism schools; and 3) participate in maintaining the quality of tourism education held by the private sector. Wonokerto Village, Wonosalam District, Jombang Regency is one of the villages that has tourism potential and superior products that are very competitive. One of the tourism potentials in Wonokerto Village is Kucur Aren Tourism. But the problem is that Kucur Aren tourism has not been managed to the maximum by residents, governments, and businessmen. The development program of Kucur Aren Tourism needs to strengthen rural institutions whose goal is to prepare and improve human resources in the development of participatory rural areas. Community participation is needed in managing Kucur Aren Tourism starting from the planning, organizing, briefing and supervision stages.

Keyword: *superior products, tourism management, community participation*

A. Introduction

Rural development has been pursued by the central government, regional governments, and the community through various policies and programs that have been established. Rural development is multidimensional and multi-sectoral. What often happens in rural areas is the development of infrastructure to support community economic activities (Bappenas, 2020). Economic activities at the village level are expected to be able to produce superior quality products and be competitive with surrounding villages. Village tourism potential does not only have potential in its superior commodities, but has cultural values, norms and customs.

Based on the terminology, tourism can be formed if there are tourism actors (demand) who do have the motivation to travel, the availability of supporting infrastructure, the existence of tourist objects and tourist attractions supported by a good promotion and marketing system as well as services to tourism actors (supply). Meanwhile, according to Law No. 10 of 2009 concerning tourism, what is meant by tourism is various kinds of tourism activities and are supported by various facilities and

services provided by the community, businessmen, government and local government. Good tourism is eco-based and sustainable tourism to maintain the balance of nature. The principles of sustainable tourism according to *World Tourism Organization* (WTO) in Koesnadi (2002:82) are as follows:

1. Natural, historical, cultural and other resources for tourism are conserved for sustainable use in the future, and can provide benefits to today's society;
2. Tourism development is planned and managed in such a way that it does not cause serious environmental and socio-cultural problems in tourist areas;
3. Overall environmental quality in the tourism area is maintained and enhanced where necessary.
4. High tourist satisfaction is maintained so that tourist destinations will still have marketability and popularity; and
5. The benefits of tourism are widespread throughout society.

According to *World Tourism Organization* (WTO), indicators that can be used to measure the level of sustainability of a tourist destination are: a) welfare (*well being*) host communities; b) protecting cultural assets; c) community participation; d) health and safety guarantees; e) economic benefits; f) protection of natural assets; g) management of scarce natural resources; h) impact limitation; and i) development planning and control. Tourism development according to Hadinoto (1996) includes several things, namely tourist attractions, promotion and marketing, the tourist market (tourist sending communities), transportation, and society. The impact of tourism is very large for local communities including increased foreign exchange earnings, community income, employment opportunities, increased prices, distribution of benefits, ownership and control, general development and increased government revenues.

According to Weaver (2010: 60) there are several stages of tourism development, namely as follows:

1. The first stage is exploration, spontaneous growth and exploratory. It can be seen that the tourist attractions are not yet known so that visitors are still small.
2. Both stages of involvement. Promotion of tourist areas can be assisted by the government in the hope that tourist attractions will be better known so as to increase the number of visits.
3. Third, the stage of development and development. With the improvement of infrastructure to increase the number of tourists who come

4. Fourth, the consolidation stage. Where development has begun to diminish and many tourists have come
5. Fifth, the stability stage. Where construction has been completed and promotions have been carried out to the fullest so that many tourists have come to the place
6. Sixth, the stage of quality decline and new birth. Namely at this stage the tourist attractions are replaced with new resorts.

Tourism in Indonesia has become a sector that can be prioritized in facilities and development. In accordance with the policy directions of the National Development Planning Agency, the development of tourism institutions consists of: 1) coordinating with tertiary institutions providing undergraduate education in the field of tourism; 2) Increasing the capacity and quality of tourism education institutions, expanding majors and demand, building tourism schools; and 3) participating in maintaining the quality of tourism education held by the private sector. In accordance with national and provincial directives, Jombang Regency encourages tourism potential by exploring issues related to tourism. The problems in the tourism sector according to the Department of Youth, Sports, Culture and Tourism are a) implementation of technical guidance and counseling in the field of culture and tourism is still lacking; b) implementation of protection, preservation, development and utilization of cultural values is still lacking; c) there is no implementation of protection, preservation, development and utilization of cultural property intellectual property rights; d) implementation of excavation, documentation and utilization of diversity culture is not maximized; e) community participation in the management of cultural wealth and diversity is not yet optimal; f) protection for Cultural Conservation Objects (BCB) has not been maximized; and g) the development and promotion of tourism is not yet optimal.

Wonokerto Village, Wonosalam District, Jombang Regency is one of the villages that has tourism potential and superior products that are very competitive. One of the tourism potentials in Wonokerto Village is Kucur Aren Tourism which presents the concept of natural and artificial tourism. On the Kucur Aren tour visitors can swim and enjoy the cool mountain air. Until now, visitors who come are not charged or free. In accordance with SE of the Minister of Home Affairs

500/1404/V/BANGDA/09, regional superior products have the following characteristics: a) are owned and controlled by the region; b) has economic value; c) highly competitive; d) high labor absorption; e) produced with technical feasibility (raw materials and markets); f) talents and local community institutions (human resources, technology, infrastructure support, local socio-cultural conditions).

With tourism development, it is hoped that tourism actors can be optimized and receive full support from *stakeholders* related. Supporting group tourism services are businesses that do not specifically offer tourism products and services but often depend on tourists as users of these services and products. The government has the authority to regulate, provide and designate various infrastructure related to tourism needs and is responsible for determining the direction in which tourist trips are headed. Local communities, especially indigenous people who live in tourist areas, are one of the key roles in tourism which will provide most of the attractions as well as quality tourism products. The problems faced by partners are as follows:

1. Partners, namely tourism and community awareness groups in Wonokerto Village, Wonosalam District, have not carried out sustainable tourism promotion planning.
2. Do not yet have a way out to overcome the management system and costs used for the development of Kucur Aren Tourism.

Picture 1. Kucur Aren Tourism Potential in Wonokerto Village, Jombang Regency.

Table 1. Results of Paired Samples Test Analysis

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Means	std. Deviation	std. Error	95% Confidence interval of the difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair Pre Test - 1 Post Test	-.250	.622	.179	-.645	.145	-1,393	11	.191

Socialization data analysis was carried out using software *Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS)* for Windows version 16.0. *Pretest and posttest* This was tested with the Paired sample t-test in order to analyze the differences between *pretest* and *posttest*. Results of *pretest* and *posttest* a scale regarding marketing using the Paired sample t –test obtained a t score of -1.393 with a result of 0.011 ($p < 0.05$) which means there is a difference between the results *pretest* and *posttest*.

The results of this socialization show that there is a difference between the pretest and posttest. Where residents experience an increase in posttest results or after being given socialization. This means that residents experience cognitive improvement in terms of understanding the importance of community awareness after being given the socialization "Increasing Community Awareness in Managing Kucur Aren Tourism". Residents who experienced an increase in outcomes *posttest* shows that residents understand the material that has been provided by the resource person/speaker. The material provided by the resource person/speaker was regarding the importance of community awareness in managing kucur aren tourism in Wonokerto village. Where the audience will be given a pretest before starting the training and a posttest after being given the training, the pretest and posttest are in the form of a statement with 5 scales regarding the importance of awareness community that will test the cognitive of residents in understanding the importance of community awareness in managing Kucur Aren tourism in Wonokerto village.

B. Methods

This research was chaired by Dida Rahmadanik and assisted by Anggraeny Puspaningtyas, Hasan Ismail, and Catur Ajeng Kartika Ria. The research that we will conduct in Kucur Aren Village is conducted qualitatively where researchers are able to interpret what is seen, felt, and encountered in the field, using data collection techniques according to the following figure:

Observation is a direct observation activity, which is expected by observing researchers can recognize the environment. In addition to observation, we will also collect data using the interview method. By conducting interviews, researchers can find out the real picture conveyed by informants, about ideal actions and information according to research needs. Documentation is a complementary technique in qualitative research, documentation studies are carried out by collecting documents and data needed in research problems. Triangulation is defined as a data collection technique that combines various data collection techniques and existing data sources.

C. Results and Discussion

Tourism Development

According to Weaver (2010: 60) there are several stages of tourism development, namely as follows:

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D. Conclusion

The implementation of community service activities in the form of socialization to increase public awareness in managing Kucur Aren Tourism in Wonokerto Village, Wonosalam District, Jombang Regency went well and met the target. Residents experienced cognitive improvement in terms of understanding the importance of community awareness after being given the socialization "Increasing Community Awareness in Managing Kucur Aren Tourism". Residents who experience an increase in posttest results show that residents understand the material that has been provided by the resource person/speaker. Based on the conclusions that have been presented, the authors propose suggestions that are considered useful and which can be considered in order to optimize the potential of Kucur Aren Tourism including:

1. Conducting Socialization to Increase Public Awareness in Managing Kucur Aren Tourism in Wonokerto Village, Wonosalam District, Jombang Regency.
2. Community and village government participation must always be maintained so that Kucur Aren's tourism potential can be optimized

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